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Review

The Frontier's Frontier: Africa, Now or Never

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Abstract: Africa, the continent with the most sovereign countries of 54, the second largest and the second most populous continent should be boasting of success if numbers and size matter. A continent with the youngest population boasting of a vibrant youth should have a working force to turn the fortunes of the continent around but things seem to be the other way round. Can Africa make it? Can Africa rise to the level it is supposed to be? Can Africa turn the tides to its favour? How true is Dr Kwame Nkrumah's assertion that "the Black man is capable of managing his own affairs"? An African adage goes, "The best time to plant a tree is twenty years ago. The second best time is now". This sheds light on how the African continent missed its first time to plant its tree of manufacturing, technological development and industrialization and that now is the opportune time for its deliverance from the shackles it finds itself bound.

Keywords: Africa, Kwame Nkrumah, manufacturing, industrialization

Africa's Economic Emancipation is Now or Never

¹Why should a continent that is believed to boast of 90% of the world's cobalt and platinum, a half of the world's gold, 98% of its chromium, 70% of its tantalite, 64% of its manganese and one-third of its uranium be lacking development? ²Why should a country like the Democratic Republic of Congo (DRC), which possesses a quantum of 70% of the world's coltan, a scarce mineral used in the production of tantalum capacitors for electronic gadgets and devices be considered a poor country? Should a country (DRC) holding 30% of the

1 "Africa: Developed Countries' Leverage On the Continent". AllAfrica.com. 7 February 2008

2 Africa, China's new frontier. Times Online. 10 February 2008

world's diamond reserves be a laughing stalk? ³Why should Guinea, the world's largest exporter of bauxite not be able to determine the price of bauxite on the world market? ⁴Why should Africa's growth be engineered by services and not manufacturing which will lead to industrialization or agriculture since there is ample proof of the fertile soils the continent possess? Why should the continent suffer with high unemployment rates since something can be done about this? Because the continent is service rendering centered, there is growth but with the lack of jobs, with little reduction in the poverty levels. With the abundance of natural resources, the continent remains the poorest and the most exploited. This punches one with deep thoughts of where and how this is possible in the first place. One would ask why the continent is in this situation. There are varied reasons to this predicament the continent finds itself in now and these can be attributed to:

Western Plundering and Exploitation

The continent became a victim and a slave to its' abundant resources. The West in their ploy to reap or take advantage of the continent masterminded the fall of most institutions and turned them against themselves in order to make the grounds fertile for their exploitation. Since the seed was already sewn in the system during the colonial era, what they needed was to water it to grow. The system is like a maze where especially the francophone countries see themselves in modern day slavery to France. ⁵It is believed that France had no interest in controlling the African nations they got involved in but to rather educate and teach them the French way of living. This is something we have all witnessed to be false. In controlling 14 African countries politically, economically and socially is something that one cannot let go because it is really absurd that about 50 per cent of these countries' foreign reserve is kept in the Central Bank of France. The French have held these African nations to an agreement which was signed out of frustrations in these African countries' hope for independence which in the end has been a mirage to these countries. Neocolonialism is eating the colonies of France to the bone. Socially these countries are totally reliant on France. Politically, these countries take no political decision without having France in mind. The amount of money held in the Bank of France is so huge that, the GDP of 14 of the Francophone countries in Africa cannot not match it and what makes it so sad is that only 15 per cent of this money is accessible to these African countries in a year and the must borrow their own money from the

³ "DR Congo poll crucial for Africa". 2006-11-16.

⁴ China tightens grip on Africa with \$4.4bn lifeline for Guinea junta. *The Times*. 13 October 2009

⁵ RasnaWarah <http://www.nation.co.ke/oped/Opinion/What-is-AU-doing-to-liberate-the-former-French-colonies/-/440808/3066624/-/11vw93z/-/>

Bank of France with the prevailing commercial rate. Our question is, how can these countries consider themselves independent states?

In order to keep the francophone nations at check, any francophone president who tried to abandon the colonial pact is killed or overthrown in a coup d'état. Sylvanus Olympio, Togo's first president was assassinated by a former sergeant of the French army when he tried to print Togo's own currency and abandon the CFA franc. Mali's first president, Modiba Keita, was lucky, he was overthrown when he decided to do same.

With the discomfort of economic and political shackles around the necks, wrists, waists and ankles of these francophone colonies, survival has become a difficult hurdle to jump over. France is in a quest to milk these nations dry and to the dismay of rightful thinking people and unions, the AU, UN and other world bodies are doing nothing to halt this barbaric nature of France. ⁶In the subjugation of these African countries, France has tied these francophone countries to its hip and which is making it difficult for these countries to move elsewhere. France is the first country these 'former colonies' can turn to with their natural resources even if there is a better offer from other places. France will first have to reject these resources before other countries can be considered; so it is with government projects and contracts. In their strive to dislodge themselves from the hip of France, the presidents of these francophone countries are threatened politically and financially by the various presidents of France. Whoever takes over as the president of France has an agenda for the colonies and it is always to the benefit of France and its companies.

The other African countries colonized by the other European nations seem to have a bit of breathing space but their economies are built to the advantage of their colonizers. The system encourages exploitation through extraction of raw materials and unprocessed minerals.

Western Media

The negative perception attributed to the African continent is a ploy by the Western media to discredit the continent through skewed movies and media reportage on Africa (Tesfaye⁷; Garrick⁸; Ogunyemi⁹; Evans and Glenn¹⁰; Michira¹¹; Kern-Foxworth¹²).

⁶ Siji Jabbar *How France loots its former colonies*, <https://thisisafrica.me/france-loots-former-colonies/>

⁷ Tesfaye AM (2014). *The Coverage of Ethiopia in BBC and CNN News Websites*. *Online J. Afr. Affairs*. 3(2): 15-25.

⁸ Garrick N (2012, July 11). *Can Media Enhance Africa's Development?* Retrieved December 3, 2014, from *The Global Journal*.

⁹ Ogunyemi O (2011). *Representation of Africa Online: Sourcing Practice and Frames of Reference*. *Journal of Black Studies*, 42(3):457-478.

Most of Africa's plight can also be associated with the Western media. Since one's image is made or unmade with the constant reportage from the media, it is imperative to be sure that what goes out is of the true reflection of the reality. The West has been able to use their media effectively as a propaganda tool to serve their interest and their interest only. The ills and shortcomings of their culprit or their targets are magnified in unprecedented proportions to dent their reputation or their capabilities. This in a larger sense has affected Africa because that is where the exploitation and the maiming of the continent begin from. When you are unmarketable, no one wants you and even your own people listening to the Western media are filled with doubt to the extent that you don't believe in your neighbour and in his or her capabilities which in the long way leaves room for exploitation. If you are unmarketable, you are either sold cheap or given out for free. So to some extent, there is goodness in the blocking of the foreign media in one's country to stop the brainwashing activities of these vultures to divide, scatter and devour. A media that only specializes in selling the negativity or the downs of one and refuses to tell of the good aspects too or to better still, a media that does not have a fair assessment of an individual or a nation is not worth listening to. The researchers for one in most aspects supports the blocking of the platforms that are capable of disorienting and misinforming their audience for their own benefit.

The New Cord

Africa has found a new friend in China. The relationship between the two is one that for the time being is seen as a win-win affair. The romance between China and Africa was not that strong until after the Bandung Conference in 1955.

From¹³, 'Africa-China relations can be traced back to Pharonic times. In the early fifteenth century there were the naval expeditions of Zheng He, followed by the importation of Chinese labour from the late eighteenth to the early twentieth centuries into the burgeoning European colonies of Mauritius, Seychelles, Madagascar and South Africa. In the first half of the twentieth century much of Africa was under colonial rule so that China's limited relations with the continent were confined to South Africa, Liberia – with which it signed a treaty of

10 Evans M, Glenn I (2010). "TIA—This is Africa": Afropessimism in Twenty-First-Century Narrative Film. *Black Camera*, 2(1)14-35.

11 Michira J (2002). *Images of Africa in the Western Media*. Retrieved September 16, 2014.

12 Kern-Foxworth M (1985). *The Effect of Advertising Stimuli on American Perception of Africa: A Descriptive Analysis*. *J. Black Stud.* 16(2):155-168.

13 Paul Tiyambe Zeleza (2014) *The Africa-China relationship: challenges and opportunities*, *Canadian Journal of African Studies / Revue canadienne des études africaines*, 48:1, 145-169

friendship in 1937 that came into force in 1941 – and semi-independent Egypt that established diplomatic relations with China in 1942’.

The reception of the Egyptian President Gamal Abdel Nasser by the Chinese Premier Zhou Enlai at the Bandung Conference in 1955 was the first diplomatic meeting between China and Africa. According to¹⁴, ‘[t]he Conference enhanced the unity and co-operation of the Asian and African countries, inspired the people in the colonies to struggle for national liberation and played a significant role in promoting the anti-imperialist and anti-colonial struggle of the Asian and African people’. Things started getting different when Chairman Mao, sought to really dispose the West off the backs of the colonized. ‘Under Chairman Mao, support was given to countries, organisations and liberation movements stretching from Egypt, to South Africa. Premier Chou Enlai made a tour of 10 Africa states between December 1963 and February 1964 and asserted that “revolutionary prospects are excellent throughout the African continent”’, M Meredith (1984)¹⁵.

Sino -Africa Engagements/Ties

China and Africa established a formal trade link in the 1950’s; the two started real cooperation from the year 2000. In 2010, 126.9 billion US dollars was the mark hit in trade from the Sino-Africa trade which was unprecedented. It is believed China sees Africa as a source of natural resources and raw or unprocessed materials but at the same time, Africa has become an export destination for Chinese products and goods. With the type of goods involved in the trade, natural resources imported from Africa is the main cause of the rise in trade. 90% of China’s import has been raw or unprocessed products since 2004. In 2009, fuel accounted for 64% of the import from Africa, iron ore and metals was next at 24%, and 5% went to food and other agricultural produce. Africa comprising of 54 countries trades differently from each other. Trade depends solely on the availability of the needed resources and how politically friendly and stable the country is. China’s trade volume with the African continent differs from countries involved Angola is the first on the line holding an annual trade volume exceeding 18.6 billion US dollars; South Africa surprisingly comes next with an annual trade volume of 16.7 billion US dollars. 76% of the total trade realized from the China-Africa trade is with the top 10 trading partners.

¹⁴ Richard Wright (1956), *The Color Curtain*, University Press of Mississippi

¹⁵ M. Meredith (1984) *The first dance of freedom: Black Africa in the post war era*, Hamilton Ltd, London.

Forum on Sino-African Ties

Table 1: China's top 10 trading partners in Africa

Country	Economic type	Average annual trade, 2006-2010 (US \$ million)	Share in total China-Africa trade
Angola	Oil export	18,627	21%
South Africa	Diversified economy	166,86	18%
Sudan	Oil export	6,445	7%
Nigeria	Oil export	5,774	6%
Egypt	Diversified economy	5,384	6%
Algeria	Oil export	4,155	5%
Libya	Oil export	4,154	5%
Republic of the Congo	Oil export	3,241	4%
Morocco	Diversified economy	2,548	3%
Benin	Agriculture	2,097	2%
Weight of top ten trading partners in total China-Africa trade			76%

Source: ¹⁶<http://www.focac.org/eng/zfgx/t820242.htm>

With the different stages of the growth of Africa's economy, one stands a great chance of saying this is really the best time for Africa to break away the shackles of economic dwarfing of the continent. With the Chinese now a major player in the world economies, and they being a developing country that has passed through all the stages of the hardships the developing nations are going through, and more so, fighting for a win-win cooperation with other developing countries, we will categorically state that it is now or never. Han Hongmei, the chairman of the China-Africa Fund for Industrial Cooperation (CAFIC), stated "In the past two and a half years, we've been focusing on supporting the development of three networks including railways, roads and aviation, as well as industrialization in Africa," (This is to the rebuttal that China is trying to colonize Africa. Han added that the investments have covered the manufacturing, communications, technology, agriculture, energy, mining, and infrastructure sectors). The figure below shows annual Chinese foreign Direct Investment outflows in Africa.

¹⁶ <http://www.focac.org/eng/zfgx/t820242.htm>

Fig 1: Chinese Annual FDI Outflows by productive sector (Manufacturing, Mining, Agriculture and ‘Other’), \$billions, 2007–15. (Source: ¹⁷National Bureau of Statistics of China (NBS) and Ministry of Commerce (MOFCOM), 2016.)

From the years past, the co-operation between the Chinese government and the governments of the African countries has moved to a different level. Co-operation between them is now not only based on political dispensation(leaders meeting) but also to the economic and social reforms. This has led to the rise in inter continental activities and is advancing intercontinental cultural exchanges. Now more of Chinese products and technical know- how are flowing toward the African continent and so are some African products and technical know- how flowing toward China. Though we can say for sure the Chinese are at the benefiting end, I believe it is a good start since there is mutual understanding between the two. There can be a sort of trade balance or co-operation balance when these African countries are able to stand on their feet in the near future and tilt the transaction in the right order. The exchanges now have been between companies, institutions and people to people

which in a way is transforming the way the two partners look at things. But a word of caution to these African nations is that, they should not take comfort in the current situation they find themselves or they will forever be dependent on the Chinese. For now, the system seem to inject a sense of purpose and belonging, as it is reported, the friendly ties between China and Africa are a perfect paradigm for Xi's concept of "a new type of international relations", what if the direction of the decision takers change? It is a well known fact that nothing is permanent in the world of politics.

¹⁷ MOFCOM, National Bureau of Statistics, State Administration of Foreign Exchange(SAFE), 2015 Statistics Bulletin of China's Foreign Direct Investment, September 2016

Challenges of the Africa-China Relationship

The relationship between China and Africa has not been smooth. Most African countries are in a crossroads and are not very sure of their bearings now due to the umbilical cord linking them and their colonizers. The model of development is not very clear. The most confusing aspect of this relationship is that, Africa keeps looking back with every single step made. The colonizers keep sounding words of caution as a sign of concern instead of accepting the current order of things. They are refusing to let go of the broken accord and leave the new-found partners alone.

It is reported that, Shu Luomei, an official with the MOC Department of Western Asian and African Affairs said "China's aid to Africa has been carried out in accordance with China's capabilities. The aid to Africa accounts for a limited proportion of China's gross domestic product," . But to most Africans, the relationship falls short in terms of job creation and contract execution. They consider the contracts to be a one sided contract which is to the benefit of the Chinese economy. Due to the lack of available data, most Africans are with the perception that, about 60% of the labour involved in the projects are being executed by the Chinese firms and companies which goes a long way to affect the labour market of the various countries in which the developmental projects are taking place. The loans are also from Chinese financial institutions like the China Exim Bank, China Development Bank, Industrial and Commercial Bank of China (ICBC), etc. More so, project advisers are mostly Chinese and the projects are executed by Chinese companies with Sinohydro taking over most of the lucrative contracts. This meaning that, the whole project benefits China economically both in short and long terms because the loans directly goes back to China. Available data on the Chinese employees in four African countries prove otherwise.

Table:2 Summary Data on Chinese Manufacturing Investments in the Four Countries

Country	# of Firms (b)	# of SOEs & JVs w/SOEs (a)	# 100 % Private	# of Investment projects (b)	Chinese employees	Local employees	Average value of projects \$ mil [c]
Ethiopia	17	2	15	18	413	8,400	9.94
Ghana	33	1	28	34	94	1,898	4.68
Nigeria	18	0	18	19	154	3,041	12.15
Tanzania	20	1	17	27	697	6,815	14.30
Total	88	4	78	98	1,358	20,154	10.26

Source: ¹⁸Brautigam, D., Xiaoyang, T., & Xia, Y. (2018)

The Way Forward

In a module we have designed, the PED module, we have made it clear that for every system to function correctly, at least, two of these three facets must work well although they are in a way inter-related.

Fig: 2 The PED module

The PED model has three main focal points, namely Political, Economy and Development. The correct management of these main focal points is the way forward for any organization.

Political

Every political organization has workable structures, and these structures should lead to good political decision making. When good political decisions are made, they may lead to a good economy or good development depending on the purpose of the decision made. A political system integrates the parts of a society into a viable functioning unit. Sometimes, that is a very difficult task. A country's political system influences how business is conducted domestically and internationally. The other two, Economy and Development are reliant on the Political. This is applicable to not only countries but also institutions, firms, etc. Some governments adopt an "individualistic paradigm" and keep intervention in the economy at a minimum range whereby the economy is basically run by individuals or conglomerates. An

18 Brautigam, D., Xiaoyang, T., & Xia, Y. (2018). What Kinds of Chinese "Geese" Are Flying to Africa? Evidence from Chinese Manufacturing Firms. Journal of African Economies, 27(suppl_1), i29-i51. doi:10.1093/jae/ejy013

example of this kind of “individualistic paradigm” is that of the US, and most European countries. Others adopt a “communitarian paradigm” wherein the government plays a larger role in the economy. They thrive on a respected, centralized bureaucracy with a stable political party or coalition in power. An example of the “communitarian paradigm” is China and North Korea. These kinds of system suits a country depending on the ideologies they embrace.

Economy

The structures that be in any society puts in place economic measures to propel development. Good economic indicators bring along investment which go a long way to ensure the sustainability of the economy. In the PED model, economy does not only refer to a country’s economy, but also, to institutions, firms, and other groups of interest being government owned, private owned or a mixture of both. If these institutions and firms are in good standing and are well resourced with the necessary amenities to operate or function properly, the mechanization of the whole country or economy will be propelled.

Development

Development is the by product of good political decisions and implementation and also, good economic policies. Development comes about when education and sensitization as good political tools play the role they are required of in any dispensation. Although development could be seen as the most dependant of the three, it is by this (development) that the other two are projected. In all developed nations, it is evident that they have a reliable political system with a flourishing economy.

Implementing a Working Developmental Plan

To know where you are going, you should have a destination. Most African nations dream of reaching where other developed nations have gotten to but they are not willing to leave behind the partisan way of doing things. Instead of instituting a national developmental plan or strategy for all other political parties to be bound to, they rather rely on party manifestos which most of the time are just promises to get them votes. And because most of the African countries rely solely on the manifestos of their parties, when there is a change in power, almost all the developmental projects of the ousted government are left to rot by the new

government and development come to a standstill because the new government has to start working on his manifesto.

In instituting a working national developmental plan, party manifestos will just provide a blueprint to achieve or implement whatever agenda the national developmental plan has in place.

Curbing Corruption

Corruption being the bane of good governance and progressiveness has held most of the African leaders by the throat and it is being condoned by their counterparts in the developed nations. The rate at which corruption is rife on the continent is worrisome. The corrupt African leaders steal from their people and stash the stolen monies and wealth in the developed countries at ease. In recent times, President Muhammadu Buhari of Nigeria responded that, the UK return the stolen assets of the corrupt leaders that are in the UK after David Cameron, UK's former Prime Minister, described some Nigerian leaders as fantastically corrupt and went further to say Nigeria and Afghanistan are possibly the most corrupt countries in the world. For the continent to develop, corruption should be frowned upon. It should emit a pungent smell whenever it crosses ones path. It is only in an African country that a sitting president can be considered richer than his own country. Political corruption is killing the dreams of the citizenry. A corrupt politician derails the progress of his/her country. Corruption is not only linked to the politicians though theirs are always easy to slip trough the fingers of the law. Corruption has become a daily routine for most civil servants. The most glaring places where corruption is rife in Ghana are the Ghana Ports and Harbour Authority, the Police Service, Immigration Service and the Ministries. It is almost so with Nigeria.

The African Dilemma

The continent is now in a crossroads and taking the right path is a headache. A continent that has been partitioned into regional blocs by its colonizers is in itself lost on the right path since all it believed in has been demonized. The pioneers of the current Africa had a dream for the continent. The likes of Dr Kwame Nkrumah of Ghana, Patrice Lumumba of Congo, Thomas Sankara of Burkina Faso, Kenneth Kaunda of Zambia etc, sought for a continent that its people could beat their chest with pride and say, yes, I am from Africa, a land full of resources, a land flowing with milk and honey, a land abound with great opportunities. But this as at the time of this publication is just a dream that could be realized after we are

awoken from our slumber, of which some say it is not even in the nearest future. The dilemma the continent finds itself now is just like a maze with meandering paths. Blog and ideological association has caught up with us which is hindering decision making. Those colonized by the French toe the line of the French, likewise those of the English etc. With new players coming into force like Malaysia, China, the UAE, etc, these African countries find themselves contemplating on the kinds of developmental model to follow. ¹⁹Bernard Adaba, policy analyst with ISODEC in Ghana said: "Development' is a lost cause in Africa while we are haemorrhaging billions every year to extractive industries, western tax havens and illegal logging and fishing. Some serious structural changes need to be made to promote economic policies that enable African countries to best serve the needs of their people rather than simply being cash cows for Western corporations and governments. The bleeding of Africa must stop!"

Aid a Canker

Aid has never helped the continent and will never help the continent. It has been a mirage which alludes both the 'genuine givers' and the recipients. These aids do not help the continent in anyway but helps the plundering of the continent since there are ulterior motives in the way and line it is given. To some extent, it has solved some problems of which has just taken away the edge to focus on the future as a better solution to dire problems. Aid cripples the economy and political leaders of a country. Most developing countries are always at the receiving end. This is used to manipulate these countries to favor a particular foreign policy or to be in the good books of powerful nations. "The West sent aid to Africa and ultimately did not care about the outcome; this created a coterie of elites and, because the vast majority of people were excluded from wealth, political instability has ensued." (Dambisa Moya, 2009,152)²⁰. These aids may be delivered by multinationals, individuals or governments. Enterprising young firms and institutions of the developing countries tend to suffer the most because these aids most of the time collapse their businesses. Tied aids kill developing countries and that is what is most of the time given to the African nations. It destroys internal markets and quenches the spirit of entrepreneurship.

¹⁹ (<http://www.oneworld.org/2017/05/17/africa-subsidises-rest-of-the-world-by-over-40-billion-a-year/>)

²⁰ Dambisa Moya (2009) *Dead Aid Why Aid Makes Things Worse And How There is Another Way For Africa, Ahead* Allen Lane Published by the Penguin Group Penguin Books Ltd, 80 Strand, London WC2R 0RL, England

Brain Drain

One major factor that hinders the progress of developing countries is brain drain.²¹ Most of those who migrate are well to do, healthier, educated, as compared to the majority that stay back. Most of these migrants are from the middle class who can really add up to the societies they find themselves in. If the growth rate of the effective human capital of a country is reduced, there is a total reduction in the per capita growth of that country (Haque and Kim 1995)²². Williamson goes on to say that, ‘the poor at the bottom were trapped, and thus stayed home; the rich at the top had a good thing going, and thus had no reason to move’. To explain further,²³ states that, “... it is actually those professionals possessing intermediate-level abilities who are hurt by brain drain”. Brain drain is sucking the milk out of the developing nations because of the lucrative remuneration and conducive working environment given to those who move to these developed nations for greener pastures. It is saddening that, these developing nations of which the majority are in Africa can do little to counter the outflow of its human capital.

Conclusion

This statement from Shawn Corey Carter (Jay-Z) “what you reveal, you heal”, is a powerful statement that is known by all but it is not practiced by all. We all know most of our problems, and they have been pointed out to us one way or the other. What are we doing to solve these problems?

Africans should think the African way and move to solve issues the way their forefathers that is the likes of Kwame Nkrumah, Thomas Sankara, Patrice Lumumba, Kenneth Kaunda, etc. apprehended the economy during their time. Africans should know that, their fate is in their own hands and they are the only ones who know where to improve. One will argue that, we are in a new era and that we should flow with modernity which of course is true but one can also state clearly that, it is based on these same forward plan for future generations in mind that these leaders laid down proper vision for their various countries of which most of these ideas and visions are clearly relevant in this modern age. The African countries should look for effective methods in implementing policies and bargain for technological transfers in the

21 Williamson, J. G. (2015). *World Migration in Historical Perspective. Handbook of the Economics of International Migration*, 89–101. doi:10.1016/b978-0-444-53764-5.09983-7

22 Haque, N.U., Kim, S.-J., 1995. “Human capital flight”: impact of migration on income and growth. *IMF Staff Papers* 42 3 , 577–607.

23 Miyagiwa, K., 1991. *Scale economies in education and the brain drain problem. International Economic Review* 32 3 , 743–759.

various contracts they sign with their new found partners as well as periodic proper training of their citizenry in the fields they lack the most. African countries should shun away from the old model of dumping of finished or semi- finished products in their various markets. One should not gloss over the achievements chalked so far. The cooperation between the African continent and China has given a tremendous hope to most Africans. The irony of the cooperation is that, it is whipping up entrepreneurial spirit among young Africans. The main focus now is for these African countries to break the trade barriers amongst them and trade within. There should be a continental intra-trade and a forward move for sustainable mutual developmental projects. It is only through self recognition, mutual respect and intra-cooperation that the francophone African countries can be emancipated and the rest of the other African countries can unite and forge a formidable front for continental development.

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